

DYNAMIC GOVERNANCE BASED BUREAUCRATIC REFORM IN SEMARANG CITY GOVERNMENT-INDONESIA

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Abstract

The Road Map of Bureaucratic Reform (RB) of Indonesian government for 2020-2024 has undergone changes in its goals and targets. Before these changes, the focus was on achieving good and clean governance. However, the revised focus is on creating a clean, effective, and competitive bureaucracy capable of driving national development and public service. The strategic targets of the RB Road Map 2020-2024 have also been simplified into two aspects: hard and soft elements. The hard element aspect aims to establish effective, agile, and collaborative digital governance as a downstream issue (thematic bureaucratic reform). The soft element aspect aims to foster a bureaucratic culture characterized by AKHLAK values (Service-Oriented, Accountable, Competent, Harmonious, Loyal, Adaptive, and Collaborative) among professional Civil Apparatus as an upstream issue (general bureaucratic reform). Digitalization acceleration has been chosen as a means to create an agile and fast bureaucracy, integrating all public needs into one grasp. This digitalization acceleration is also seen as a way to transform bureaucratic reform into dynamic governance by 2025. It makes the bureaucracy more effective and efficient, characterized by agility and adaptability. Hence, it is on par with world-class bureaucracy standards.

Keywords: Bureaucratic Reform; Dynamic Governance; Government.

1. INTRODUCTION

The grand design for bureaucratic reform is a fundamental framework providing strategic direction and policy for both central and regional governments to achieve the national bureaucratic reform goals set from 2010 to 2025.

As a follow-up to Presidential Regulation Number 81 of 2010 on the Grand Design of Bureaucratic Reform 2010-2025, several regulations have been established, such as Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 135 of 2018 on Accelerating the Implementation of Bureaucratic Reform in Regional Governments, Minister for Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform Regulation Number 25 of 2020 on the Bureaucratic Reform Road Map 2020-2024, amended by Minister for Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform Regulation Number 3 of 2023, and it is strengthened by Minister for Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform Regulation Number 9 of 2023 on the Evaluation of Bureaucratic Reform.

The vision stated in Minister for Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform Regulation Number 25 of 2020 on the Bureaucratic Reform Road Map 2020-2024, as amended by Regulation Number 3 of 2023, is to achieve a World-Class Government (a government free from Corruption, Collusion, and Nepotism; Professional and Providing Excellent Service). This vision can be illustrated as follows:

Figure 1: Achieving a World-Class Government (A Government free from Corruption, Collusion, and Nepotism; Professional and Providing Excellent Service)

Source: Processed from Minister for Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform Regulation Number 25 of 2020 in conjunction with Minister for Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform Regulation Number 3 of 2023 on the Bureaucratic Reform Road Map 2020-2024

The Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 135 of 2018 on Accelerating the Implementation of Bureaucratic Reform in Regional Governments also states that there are two goals for accelerating the implementation of bureaucratic reform, to achieve good governance in regional governments based on performance and dynamic governance and to promote the acceleration of comprehensive bureaucratic reform implementation within regional governments. Dynamic governance, according to Neo & Chen (2007), is defined as the government's ability to continuously adapt its policies and public programs and to change the way they formulate and implement them to achieve the nation's long-term interests. Dynamic governance involves continuous learning, quick and effective execution, and endless change marked by new ideas, new perceptions, sustainability improvements, quick action, flexible adaptation, and creative innovation. Neo & Chen (2007) illustrated the dynamic governance framework with the following diagram:

Figure 2: Dynamic Governance Framework

Source: Adopted from Neo & Chen (2007).

The main elements of dynamic governance within the Neo & Chen (2007) framework are contingent on the organizational culture of government and dynamic capabilities supported by able people and agile processes.

Dynamic governance can be achieved when adaptive policies are implemented. Three dynamic capabilities leading to adaptive policies consist of forward thinking, rethinking, and thinking across. These dynamic capabilities are driven by able people and agile processes. The external environment also influences governance systems through future uncertainties and external practices.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This research employed a doctrinal approach (legal research). Doctrinal research is based on legislative, conceptual, and case approaches (Marzuki, 2014). The methods used include, Philosophical Approach and Statute Approach. They were conducted by examining laws and regulations related to the legal issues at hand and a conceptual approach, which stems from perspectives and doctrines evolving within the field of law (Marzuki, 2014).

Data analysis was carried out descriptively qualitatively, elucidated through non-statistical linguistic argumentation, and conclusions are formulated through deductive-inductive reasoning. Qualitative analysis is a study that starts from reality with the basic assumption that human behavior has meaning for the actor in a particular context (Miles et al., 2014).

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Bureaucratic Reform, Road Map, Regional Government

Bureaucratic reform is the process of restructuring bureaucracy from the highest to the lowest levels and making new breakthroughs with gradual, concrete, realistic, serious, out-of-the-box, paradigm-shifting, and extraordinary efforts.

Bureaucratic reform itself is carried out through the establishment of the Grand Design of Bureaucratic Reform to be used as a master plan containing the direction of national bureaucratic reform policy implementation for the period 2010-2025.

Bureaucracy, in a narrow sense according to Effendi (2013), is defined as government organizations, while the broader understanding of bureaucracy is a system operated by government employees.

The governmental system consists of administrative systems, government management systems, and institutional systems that encompass organizational structures, employees, and institutional infrastructure. Government employees include career and non-career employees as long as they perform government duties.

The concept of bureaucratic reform, as conveyed by Quah in Iqrom (2013), is a process to change the processes, procedures of public bureaucracy, and attitudes as well as behaviors of bureaucrats to achieve bureaucratic effectiveness and national development goals..

The success of implementing bureaucratic reform is affected by several factors. According to Prasojo & Kurniawan (2008), the main factors affecting bureaucratic reform are:

- a) Political will and leadership commitment;
- b) The role of stakeholders in preparing program implementation priorities, monitoring and evaluating programs;
- c) There are development programs in all sectors as well as efforts to change the bureaucratic paradigm and culture; and
- d) Selection of program priorities that are right on target.

The objective found in the RB Road Map 2020-2024 before refinement was "Good and clean governance", while the objective after refinement is "Clean, effective, and competitive bureaucracy driving national development and public service". In the RB Road Map 2020-2024 after refinement, the strategic targets of RB are simplified into two aspects: hard and soft elements. Hard elements are intended to create an effective, agile, and collaborative digital governance, while soft elements are intended to create a bureaucratic culture with *BerAKHLAK* (*Berorientasi Pelayanan, Akuntabel, Kompeten, Harmonis, Loyal, Adaptif, dan Kolaboratif*/Service-Oriented, Accountable, Competent, Harmonious, Loyal, Adaptive, and Collaborative) Civil Servants (ASN). Thus, ASN can become professionals.

The main activity of bureaucratic reform after refining the RB Road Map 2020-2024 is now no longer linked to eight areas of change but will be focused on implementing acceleration activities aimed at speeding up the realization of digital bureaucracy. Digitalization acceleration is believed to bring about a transformation of bureaucratic reform by 2025 into dynamic governance, where bureaucracy becomes more effective and efficient with agile and adaptive characteristics, thus matching world-class bureaucracy (Taufiq, 2023). The refinement of the RB Road Map 2020-2024, as outlined in Minister of PANRB Regulation No. 3 of 2023 amending Minister of PANRB Regulation No. 25/2020 on the Road Map of Bureaucratic Reform 2020-2024, also focuses on addressing upstream issues referred to as General Bureaucratic Reform, which are governance issues occurring within the bureaucracy, and downstream issues referred to as Thematic Bureaucratic Reform. They are issues arising in society and related to the priority agenda of national development.

Currently, government institutions believe that implementing digital services is sufficient to become a digital organization. However, true digital transformation focuses on fundamental changes in mindset and working methods, shifting from "doing digital" to "being digital". Based on data released by Deloitte (Taufiq, 2023), there are four phases of digital transformation. The first phase begins with "beginning digital," bureaucracy only provides digital platforms such as websites as sources of information for public services. The second phase is "doing digital," where digital technology applied can enhance public services but does not change the mindset of service managers; their mindset remains conventional. The third phase is "becoming digital," the application of digital technology is comprehensive, although a small portion still combines physical and digital services. This transformation has been made but still requires cognitive intelligence for continuous improvement. The fourth phase is "being digital," humans have fully transformed towards digitalization, utilizing artificial intelligence, cloud, and other technologies for delivering all public services. This will

continue to be the direction in the future. Road Map is a detailed and sustainable work plan that outlines the implementation of bureaucratic reform over the next 5 (five) years. The Bureaucratic Reform Road Map is an operational form of the Grand Design of Bureaucratic Reform, prepared and executed every 5 (five) years. It represents a detailed plan for implementing bureaucratic reform from one stage to the next over a five-year period, with clear targets for each year. Based on Bob Galvin in Phaal, Farrukh, & Probert (2015), a road map is a broad vision of the future for a selected field, consisting of collective knowledge and imagination as the smartest driver of change in that field. Hasse & Weingaertner (2016) defined a road map as a strategic planning and design instrument that is appealing because it offers to broaden the perspective and effectiveness of conventional planning methods and also allows for reflection and strategic handling of uncertainty and insecurity. According to Ho & O'Sullivan (2017), a road map is essentially a technique used in strategy development consisting of the following steps:

- a) Vision and goals: establishing direction in terms of future vision and goals;
- b) Current position assessment: collecting and assessing available information, relating to current and past strategies, activities and performance;
- c) Assessment of the external and internal environment. External environmental assessments are intended to collect and assess information relating to external factors, issues, and drivers to identify opportunities and threats. Internal environmental assessments are intended to collect and assess information relating to internal resources, capabilities, and constraints, to identify strengths and weaknesses;
- d) Generate and assess strategic options: generate strategic options, identify gaps, and assess and select options to obtain a strategic plan;
- e) Implementation: turning strategic plans into action; and
- f) Evaluation and learning: reviewing results and disseminating results.

Regional Government is an institution that carries out the functions of regional government together with the regional representative council. Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government states that regional government is the implementation of government affairs based on the principle of autonomy and the task of decentralization with the widest possible autonomy in the system and principles of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. The functions of regional government, according to Setiawan (2018), are as follow:

- a) As an extension of the central government, to bring the state closer to the community;
- b) As a regional development planner;
- c) As organizer of affairs delegated by the central government; And
- d) As a regional policy maker.

2. Bureaucratic Reform in the Semarang City Government

2.1 The Purpose of Bureaucratic Reform (RB) in the Semarang City Government

The Government of Semarang City has responded to the directive for the formation of the Bureaucratic Reform Road Map, which has undergone changes. This is regulated

in Mayor Regulation Number 8 of 2022 concerning Amendments to Semarang City Mayor Regulation Number 66 of 2020 concerning the Bureaucratic Reform Road Map of the Semarang City Government for the Period 2020-2024. This is carried out with consideration that in order to adjust to the Medium-Term Development Plan of Semarang City for the Period 2021-2026 as stipulated in Semarang City Regional Regulation Number 6 of 2021 concerning the Medium-Term Development Plan of Semarang City for the Period 2021-2026, Semarang City Mayor Regulation Number 66 of 2020 concerning the Bureaucratic Reform Road Map of the Semarang City Government for the Period 2020-2024 needs to be reviewed. The follow-up implementation of bureaucratic reform primarily at the institutional/micro level, therefore, requires the preparation of Amendments to the Bureaucratic Reform Road Map for the Period 2023-2024, especially after the issuance of Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia Regulation Number 3 of 2023 concerning Amendments to Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia Regulation Number 25 of 2020 concerning the Bureaucratic Reform Road Map 2020-2024, with priority on:

- 1) The emphasis is on the preparation of General Bureaucratic Reform, which aims to create an effective, agile, and collaborative digital governance and the creation of a Bureaucracy with *BerAKHLAK*, with Professional Civil Servants;
- 2) Emphasis on preparing Thematic Bureaucratic Reform with focus:
 - (a) Poverty Alleviation
 - (b) Increased Investment,
 - (c) Government Digitalization (Stunting Alleviation),
 - (d) Increased Use of Domestic Products (P3DN) and
 - (e) Inflation Control.

The description of the objectives of the Semarang City Bureaucratic Reform Road Map Changes for 2023-2024 can be seen in the table below:

Table 1: Purpose of Changes to the Semarang City Bureaucratic Reform Road Map for 2023-2024

Purpose	Indicator	Unit	Baseline 2022	Target	
				2023	2024
The purpose is to achieve a bureaucracy that is clean, effective, and competitive, supporting national development and public services.	Regional Government Bureaucratic Reform Index Achievements	Indeks	72,68	74,00	76,00
	The performance indicators for development achievements include poverty reduction rates and investment growth rates.	Percent	16,10	15,80	15,50
		Rupiah	22.164.705 .670.019	25.684.059. 000.000	27.362.089. 00 0.000

Source: Processed from Semarang Mayor Regulation Number 62 of 2023 concerning Road Map for Semarang City Government Bureaucratic Reform in 2023-2024

2.2 Strategic Targets of Bureaucratic Reform (RB) in the Semarang City Government

The targets to be achieved by the Semarang City Government are focused on efforts to create digital government governance that is effective, agile, collaborative and accountable. The implementation and achievement of these Strategic Targets consists of 9 targets consisting of: :

1. Implementation of Bureaucratic Simplification Policy.
2. Implementation of the New Work System Policy with a Flexible Model for Civil Servants Well.
3. Implementation of the national Electronic Based Government System (SPBE) architecture policy. Problems in relation to the implementation of SPBE in Semarang City are:
 - a) Regional Apparatus Organizations (OPD) do not understand the business processes related to their respective duties, so that formulating and building systems for services is less than optimal and becomes a problem in itself.
 - b) OPD does not understand its duties as data manager and producer and only creates systems casuistically. In the end, the system is not managed properly, becomes application waste in the data center and is vulnerable to cyber threats.
4. The implementation of an integrated Planning, Budgeting, and Performance Information System based on information technology that drives the improvement of performance accountability in government agencies.
5. The establishment of Digital Public Service (*Digital Services*)

Currently, the Semarang City Government already has a Public Service Mall (MPP) where the public can process 225 types of services from 15 Regional Apparatus Organizations (OPDs) in Semarang City through the MPP..
6. Improving the Quality of Supervision

An aspect that needs to be strengthened in implementing bureaucratic reform is oversight. This can be conducted through improving the quality of the government's internal supervisory apparatus (APIP) and internal control systems (SPIP). The assessment results from the Financial and Development Supervisory Agency (BPKP) in 2022 indicate that the SPIP maturity level in Semarang city is 3.012. This figure has exceeded the target planned in the Semarang City Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMD) for 2022, which was set at 2.7. In other words, the achievement of SPIP maturity is 89.64% or falls into the high category.
7. Increasing the Quality of Policies and Regulations.
8. Increasing the Quality of Management of Digital Archives and Statistical Data.
9. Increasing the quality of government procurement of goods and services, financial and asset management.

A description of the targets for changes to the Semarang City Bureaucratic Reform Road Map for 2023-2024 can be seen in the table below.

Table 2: Target Changes to the Semarang City Bureaucratic Reform Roadmap for 2023-2024

Target	Indicator	Unit	Baseline (2022)	Target	
				2023	2024
The realization of Agile, Collaborative, and Accountable Digital Government Governance.	SPBE Index	Score	3,38	3,6	3,9
	SAKIP score	Score/rank	>72/BB	>74/BB	>76/BB
	BPK opinion	Status	WTP	WTP	WTP
The realization of a Culture of <i>BerAKHLAK</i> Bureaucracy with Professional Civil Servants (ASN).	BerAKHLAK Index	Index	NA	72	72,60
	Integrity Assessment Survey Values	Score	NA	78,2	78,3
	Community Satisfaction Survey Values	Score	88	88,35	91,02

Source: Processed from Semarang Mayor Regulation Number 62 of 2023 concerning Road Map for Semarang City Government Bureaucratic Reform in 2023-2024.

Note: BerAKHLAK is an acronym for *Ber = Berorientasi Pelayanan* (Service Oriented), *A = Accountable*, *K = Kompeten* (Competent), *H = Harmonious*, *L = Loyal*, *A = Adaptive*, *K = Kolaboratif* (Collaborative). BerAKHLAK is established as the Core Value for all Civil Servants in carrying out their duties and responsibilities.

4. CONCLUSION

The urgency and importance of implementing Bureaucratic Reform at the central level have been marked by the issuance of Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia Regulation Number 3 of 2023 concerning Amendments to Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia Regulation Number 25 of 2020 concerning the Bureaucratic Reform Road Map 2020-2024. It is due to changes that are based on the consideration that. First, the impact of bureaucratic reform in supporting the achievement of national development goals and Indonesia's competitiveness on the international stage has not been optimal, thus requiring a refinement of the cause-and-effect relationships and alignment of the conditions to be achieved at the impact level with the focus level of bureaucratic reform implementation. Second, in refining the cause-and-effect relationships and aligning the conditions, substantive changes related to the goals and objectives of bureaucratic reform, reform activities that have an impact, the focus of bureaucratic reform implementation, and the refinement of bureaucratic reform indicators are needed.

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